

Probabilistic seismic hazard and risk assessment of Thessaloniki, Greece

Stefania Apostolaki – Aristotle University, Thessaloniki, Greece, aestefan@civil.auth.gr

Evi Riga – Aristotle University, Thessaloniki, Greece, eviriga@civil.auth.gr

Dimitris Pitilakis – Aristotle University, Thessaloniki, Greece, dpitilakis@civil.auth.gr

Abstract Seismic hazard and risk assessment are of significant importance for many sectors, e.g., the insurance industry, as they can significantly affect many socio-economic factors. The efficiency of the seismic hazard and risk assessment process is based on the accuracy of the models used and their capability to manage to some extent the multi-nature sources of uncertainties involved in all stages. In this study, we use a fully probabilistic method to evaluate the seismic hazard for Thessaloniki, Greece, and the seismic risk of its residential buildings. For the seismic hazard assessment, we perform an Event-Based PSHA using as input the European Seismic Hazard Model ESHM20 and a very detailed site model developed for Thessaloniki using the available data from the microzonation study. We present seismic hazard maps for two different intensity measures and a set of return periods and hazard curves at four different locations with different site conditions. For the seismic risk, we perform a Stochastic Event-Based Probabilistic Seismic Damage Analysis for the residential buildings of Thessaloniki using the European Seismic Risk Model (ESRM20) vulnerability models. Seismic risk results are presented in terms of expected structural damage and economic losses for various return periods.

Keywords: seismic hazard, seismic risk, ESHM20, ESRM20

1. Introduction

Seismic hazard and risk assessment are essential for many sectors, e.g., the insurance industry, as they can significantly affect many socio-economic factors. They are, therefore, a critical step in strategies related to the reduction of earthquake-induced losses at local, urban, national, and even continental scales. The efficiency of the seismic hazard and risk assessment process is based on the accuracy of the models used and their capability to manage the multi-nature sources of uncertainties involved in all stages (Riga et al., 2017). In the past few years, many seismic risk assessment studies used probabilistic methods to consider the arbitrary nature of this natural phenomenon (e.g., Silva et al., 2014b, Rao et al., 2020).

In this study, we use a fully probabilistic method for the seismic hazard assessment of the city of Thessaloniki, Greece, as well as for the seismic risk assessment of its residential buildings, using components of the newly developed open-access European Seismic Hazard (ESHM20, Danciu, et al., 2021) and Risk Models (ESRM20, Crowley, et al., 2021). Both models were developed within Horizon 2020 EU SERA project (<http://www.sera-eu.org/en/home/>) and are available online at the European Facilities for Earthquake Hazard and Risk (EFEHR, <http://www.efehr.org>).

Thessaloniki is the second-largest city in Greece and is very well documented in terms of local site conditions and exposure. The study area examined in this work consists of 16 municipalities, as shown in Figure 1. For the seismic hazard assessment of Thessaloniki, we performed an Event-Based Probabilistic Seismic Hazard Analysis (PSHA) with the

OpenQuake-Engine (Pagani et al., 2014; Silva et al., 2014a) using as input the ESHM20 seismogenic source model and ground motion model and a very detailed site model developed for Thessaloniki using the available data from the microzonation study (Riga et al., 2022). The seismic hazard is expected to be considerably high as the area's seismicity is affected by the Mygdonia and Anthemountas active faults, which are associated with severe earthquakes with magnitude up to $M_w = 7.0$ (Papazachos and Papazachou, 1997). For instance, the 1978 earthquake ($M_w=6.5$, $R = 30\text{km}$) led to severe damages at about 4000 buildings and caused 47 fatalities and 220 injuries (Penelis et al., 1988).

Regarding the seismic risk assessment, we performed an Event-Based Probabilistic Seismic Damage Analysis using the OpenQuake-Engine for the residential buildings of the study area constructed with either reinforced concrete or masonry, which are around 75,000 according to the results of the building census of 2011 for Greece (ELSTAT). Each of these buildings was classified to an appropriate building category using the GED4ALL Building Taxonomy (Brzev et al., 2021), a uniform classification system developed by the Global Earthquake Model (GEM). This taxonomy system is adopted in the European Seismic Risk Model (ESRM20) fragility and vulnerability models (Romão et al., 2021), which we used to perform Stochastic Event-Based Probabilistic Seismic Damage analysis. Seismic risk results are presented in terms of expected damages and economic losses for multiple return periods.

Fig. 1 – Study area of Thessaloniki consisting of 16 municipalities.

2. Local site conditions and seismic hazard assessment

Thessaloniki the second largest city in Greece and is very well-documented in terms of local site conditions as several laboratory and in-situ geophysical and geotechnical tests have been carried out to validate the dynamic properties and geometry of its main soil formations and develop detailed geotechnical maps, 1-D profiles, and 2-D cross-sections in the framework of its microzonation study (Anastasiadis et al., 2001). Figure 2 illustrates the spatial distribution of $V_{s,30}$ based on the microzonation study for a grid of approximately 1×1 km consisting of 142 points and covering the whole study area (Riga et al., 2022). Based on this map, the coastal area is characterized by soft soil formations with low $V_{s,30}$ values. In contrast, in the north-east part the $V_{s,30}$ values are greater than 800 m/s, indicating rock-like formations and, thus, classified as soil type A according to Eurocode 8.

Fig. 2 - Spatial distribution of $V_{s,30}$ (m/s) in the study area on the detailed site model developed from the microzonation study of Thessaloniki, applied for seismic hazard assessment. The classification of the study area according to EC8 (CEN, 2004) based on the detailed site model is also included in the figure.

This detailed site model was used as input in the PSHA analysis that we performed in OpenQuake software, along with the ESHM20 seismogenic source and logic tree models (Danciu et al., 2021). We used the Event-Based Probabilistic Seismic Hazard calculator, which generates a large number of stochastic event sets (SES) that contain multiple possible earthquake scenarios using a Monte Carlo process and logic-tree methods for the seismic sources and the Ground Motion Prediction Equations (GMPEs). The calculator provides seismic hazard maps and hazard curves for each event set and the respective mean and quantile outputs. An extended and detailed explanation of the PSHA calculator is presented in GEM (2012).

The resulting mean hazard maps of the Peak Ground Acceleration, PGA, and spectral acceleration at 1.0s, $S_a(1.0s)$, for the return periods of 101, 475, 975, and 2500 years, are illustrated in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, respectively. We should note that such analyses can provide results for multiple intensity measures and types. However, we are interested more in the values of PGA and spectral accelerations, S_a , at 0.3s, 0.6s, and 1.0s, which are then used in the fragility and the vulnerability functions of ESRM20 for the risk assessment. Higher values of PGA are obtained for the coastal area with soft-soil formations, while lower values are estimated for the rock-based northern-east part of the city (Fig. 3). Indeed, for the hazard scenario of 475 years, the PGA is almost 0.51 g in the coastal area, while in the northeast, it is as high as 0.35 g. As expected, the higher the examined return period, the higher the PGA values.

The spectral acceleration at 1 s period, $S_a(1.0s)$, is the most common intensity measure adopted to describe the seismic behavior of the buildings in this area (Pitilakis et al., 2022). Similar conclusions for the PGA can be derived for the $S_a(1.0s)$. For the most commonly used hazard scenario of 475 years, the $S_a(1.0s)$ in the city center of Thessaloniki reaches the value of 0.32 g, while in the northeast part of the city, e.g., the regions of Pefka, Sykies, Triandria, north Pylaia and north Panorama (see Fig. 1) the average $S_a(1.0s)$ value is 0.16 g. For the more devastating hazard scenario of 2500 years, $S_a(1.0s)$ ranges from 0.25 g to 0.85 g.

Fig. 3 – Hazard maps in PGA terms for the return periods of a) 101 years, b) 475 years, c) 975 years, and d) 2500 years.

Fig. 4 – Hazard map in Sa(1.0s) terms for the return periods of a) 101 years, b) 475 years, c) 975 years, and d) 2500 years.

Fig. 5 shows the hazard curves in terms of PGA and Sa(1.0s) for four examined regions: Evosmos (blue line), Thessaloniki city center (red line), Kalamaria (orange line), and Pefka (green line). The lowest probabilities of exceedance are assigned to the Pefka municipality, situated on very stiff soil. The highest probabilities of exceedance are assigned to the main city center of Thessaloniki at all ranges of PGA and Sa(1.0s). Riga et al. (2022) indicated the significant discrepancies of the estimated seismic hazard that can be found when moving from a large-scale analysis, e.g., for the whole city, to a smaller scale, as was also found in the present study.

Fig. 5 – Hazard curves in terms of PGA (left) and Sa(1.0s) (right) for the four examined regions: 1) Evosmos with the blue line, 2) Thessaloniki city center with the red line, 3) Kalamaria with the orange line and 4) Pefka with the green line.

3. Seismic risk assessment in terms of physical damages

In our region of interest, there are 75,169 residential buildings constructed from reinforced concrete or masonry according to the building census of 2011 for Greece (ELSTAT). We used the exposure model by Ptilakis et al. (2022), who assigned each of the buildings of every census sector to the building type categories of the GED4ALL Building Taxonomy (Brzev et al., 2021), according to critical attributes that characterize the seismic behavior, i.e., primary construction material, lateral load resisting system, height, and ductility level, which is assumed to be a function of the period of construction. The census sector is the geographic unit adopted by ELSTAT for the census and contains an average of 600 residences. 69.6% of the buildings are reinforced concrete structures with infilled frames, while 24.5% have a dual lateral load resisting system with infilled frames and walls. Almost half of the examined building stock is assigned to the low ductility category, as they have been constructed between 1960 and 1985, thus designed with the first, but not adequate, seismic code in Greece.

This taxonomy scheme is adopted by the European Seismic Risk Model (ESRM20, Crowley, et al., 2021) fragility and vulnerability models (Romão et al., 2021), which we applied for the seismic risk assessment analysis. For this, we used the Stochastic Event-Based Probabilistic Seismic Damage calculator of the OpenQuake-Engine, which estimates the expected damages for individual assets, as well as the aggregated damage for a spatially distributed portfolio of assets. To do so, it employs an event-based Monte Carlo simulation approach to produce a large set of possible ground motion realizations that characterize the probabilistic nature of the damage assessment. For each ground motion realization, a damage state is simulated for each building of every asset in the exposure model using the provided fragility model (GEM, 2012).

One of the primary seismic risk outputs regards the expected average annual number of buildings in each damage state, which was used to produce risk maps with the percentages of buildings expected to show greater than slight or complete damage (Fig. 6). The highest percentages are found at the historical center of the city, which can be attributed not only to the high seismic hazard of the area (see the previous section) but also to the low seismic design level of the majority of the buildings in this area, as almost 60% of the buildings have been constructed before 1985. The annual probability for the buildings in this area to show slight to complete damage (i.e., excluding the buildings with no damage) is up to 0.4%. On the other hand, the relatively new building stock of Pefka municipality (see Fig. 1) and the low seismic hazard in this region explains the lowest expected risk in this area. Regarding the study area as a whole, the annual percentage of the buildings expected to show no damage is 99.8%. In comparison, the annual percentage of buildings expected to exceed the complete damage state is 0.03%. Similar levels of seismic risk in terms of the expected number of collapsed buildings were noticed by Crowley et al. (2009) and Dolce et al. (2020) for many cities in Italy.

Another significant thing to notice is that the considerable spatial variation of the seismic hazard and the affected building taxonomies result in significant spatial differentiations of the estimated risk, as shown in Fig. 6. This indicates the need for high-resolution analysis in terms of exposure modelling, as was the case in the present application, where the information in the adopted exposure model was available at the census sector level.

Fig. 6 – Average annual damage maps in terms of the percentage of buildings which annually exceed the slight damage state (left) or complete damage state (right)

4. Seismic risk assessment in terms of economic losses

We added a consequences model to the event-based probabilistic analysis described above to estimate the expected economic losses. This model includes the loss indices (which is the ratio of repair cost to the cost of replacement) for every taxonomy based on the vulnerability model of ESRM20 (Romão et al., 2021). The following loss indices were adopted: 0.05 (slight damage), 0.15 (moderate damage), 0.6 (extensive damage), 1.0 (complete damage).

Fig. 7 shows the loss ratio maps for the return periods of 50, 200, 500, and 1000 years. We should highlight that this return period is referred to the risk part of the analysis. The tendency of the spatial distribution is the same for all the return periods, with higher values at the coastal area of the city and lower at the northeast part, following the distribution of the

expected damages. As was expected, the higher the return period, the higher the expected damages and, thus, the expected losses or loss ratio. According to the most devastating scenario of 1000 years, the maximum loss ratio is as high as 65% in the coastal area, while it is expected to be less than 15% for almost half of the study area. The average loss ratio assigned to the 200 years return period, which is a standard risk metric, is 19% at the coastal area of the main city center, while for the Pefka municipality, it is almost 0.5%. For the Kalamaria region, the mean expected loss ratio of 200 years return period scenario is 6%, but within this municipality of 7,7 km² area there are considerable discrepancies of the loss ratio (from 0.6% to 15%). These big discrepancies indicate the need for analysis at the smallest possible scale.

Fig. 7 – Expected loss ratio map for the risk return periods of a) 50 years, b) 200 years, c) 500 years, and d) 1000 years.

Finally, in Fig. 8, we illustrate the loss exceedance curve, which describes the expected economic losses for the entire study area's multiple return periods (or annual frequencies of exceedance). The Gross Domestic Product 2020 (GDP) for Greece (217,7 billion €) is used for displaying the relative to the national GDP loss values on the labels. The losses at the 100-year and the 200-year return periods are 1.2 billion € (0,56% GDP) and 2.6 billion € (1,18% GDP), respectively.

The aggregate loss ratio for the whole study area at the 200-return period scenario is 7.3%, but it ranges from 0.1% to 25% at the census-sector level. This range increases as the examined return period increases. Indeed, for the risk return period of 1,000 years, the aggregate loss ratio for the whole study area is 19% (Fig. 8), but at the census-sector scale it varies from 1% to 65% (Fig. 7). The impact of exposure spatial resolution on seismic loss estimates in regional portfolios was highlighted by Dabbeek et al. (2021) and Fayjaloun et al. (2021).

Fig. 8 – Loss exceedance curve for Thessaloniki. The 2020 nominal GDP (217.7 billion €) is used for displaying the relative loss values on the labels.

5. Conclusions and discussion

This paper contributes to creating a probabilistic seismic risk model for the second largest city of Greece, Thessaloniki. Thessaloniki has suffered severe earthquakes in the past, which justifies the need for special studies and further examination. Its wide variety in terms of local site conditions and building categories amplifies the interest of the area.

The open-source OpenQuake-Engine software was employed to perform probabilistic seismic hazard and risk analyses, leading to several significant results. We performed an event-based probabilistic seismic hazard analysis, considering the most recent and updated seismogenic source models and ground motion models of ESHM20. We also performed event-based probabilistic analyses for the risk component. The main outputs were multiple risk metrics like loss exceedance curves and loss maps for both the expected damages and estimated structural economic losses.

Regarding the hazard, stronger earthquake ground motions are expected in the coastal area, while the hazard in the rest of the region of interest is reduced. For instance, for the most commonly used hazard scenario of 475 years, the expected PGA and Sa(1.0s) for the coastal area are 0.51g and 0.32g, when for the northern east part of the city, they are expected to be almost 0.35g and 0.16g, respectively. The tendency is the same when moving from hazard to expected structural damages and economic losses. The most vulnerable region is the city center, where the high seismic hazard is combined with the relatively old building stock.

In addition, although the probabilistic analysis can provide aggregate values of any seismic risk metric for the whole study area, we noticed significant discrepancies when moving to a smaller scale. The higher the resolution of the exposure model, the higher the capability of the analysis to predict risk at a small scale and, thus, to efficiently contribute to the efforts for seismically sustainable cities. Dabbeek et al. (2021) examined and endorsed the high impact of the exposure spatial resolution in seismic risk assessment and, more specifically, to the average annual loss (ALL) estimation.

Riga et al. (2022), performed a seismic risk analysis for Thessaloniki considering only the seismic hazard with a 475-year, which, besides, is the most widely adopted return period for

the seismic design of structures. We calculated both the hazard and the risk components for multiple return periods through an event-based probabilistic process for further investigation. At this point, we should note that the return periods of the hazard and risk components are not directly related. The results indicated that: a) both the seismic hazard and the seismic risk follow more or less the same tendency throughout the return periods examined, with the coastal part of the study area, where the central city and historical center are located, to be more vulnerable than the rest of the area, b) the need for more specific and high-resolution exposure and site model is more urgent for high return periods, where the aggregated risk values are not representative for the whole study area.

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References

- Anastasiadis, A., Raptakis, D., Pitilakis, K.: Thessaloniki's detailed microzoning: subsurface structure as basis for site response analysis. *Pure and Applied Geophysics*, 158 (12), 2597–2633 (2001)
- Brzev, S., Silva, V., Allen, L., Scawthorn, C., Yepes, C., Dabbeek, J., Crowley, H. (2021) A building classification scheme for multi-hazard risk assessment. Submitted to *Natural Hazards and Earthquake System Sciences*.
- Crowley, H., Dabbeek J., Despotaki, V., Rodrigues, D., Martins, L., Silva, V., Romão, X., Pereira, N., Weatherill, G., Danciu, L. (2021) European Seismic Risk Model (ESRM20). EFEHR Technical Report 002 V1.0.0, <https://doi.org/10.7414/EUC-EFEHR-TR002-ESRM20>.
- Dabbeek, J., Crowley, H., Silva, V., Weatherill, G., Paul, N., & Nievas, C. I. (2021). Impact of exposure spatial resolution on seismic loss estimates in regional portfolios. *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering*, 19(14), 5819–5841. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10518-021-01194-x>
- Danciu, L., Nandan, S., Reyes, C., Basili, R., Weatherill, G., Beauval, C., Rovida, A., Vilanova, S., Sesetyan, K., Bard, P-Y., Cotton, F., Wiemer, S., Giardini, D. (2021a) The 2020 update of the European Seismic Hazard Model: Model Overview. EFEHR Technical Report 001, v1.0.0, <https://doi.org/10.12686/a15>.
- ELSTAT (2011): 2011 Population-Housing Census, Hellenic Statistical Authority
- Fayjaloun, R., Negulescu, C., Roullé, A., Auclair, S., Gehl, P., & Faravelli, M. (2021). Sensitivity of earthquake damage estimation to the input data (Soil characterization maps and building exposure): Case study in the Luchon Valley, France. *Geosciences (Switzerland)*, 11(6). <https://doi.org/10.3390/geosciences11060249>
- GEM (2012) OpenQuake manual. <https://www.globalquakemodel.org/openquake/support/documentation>
- Kotha SR, Weatherill G, Bindi D, Cotton F (2020): A regionally-adaptable ground-motion model for shallow crustal earthquakes in Europe. *Bull Earthquake Eng* 18: 4091–4125, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10518-020-00869-1>
- Papazachos B, Papazachou C. (1997): The earthquakes of Greece. Ziti Editions, Thessaloniki.
- Penelis GG, Sarigiannis D, Stavrakakis E, Stylianidis KC (1988): A statistical evaluation of damage to buildings in the Thessaloniki, Greece, earthquake of June 20, 1978. *Proceedings of Ninth World Conference on Earthquake Engineering, Tokyo-Kyoto, Japan, August 1988, Tokyo: Maruzen; 1988. p. VII:187–92.*
- Rao, A., Dutta, D., Kalita, P., Ackerley, N., Silva, V., Raghunandan, M., Ghosh, J., Ghosh, S., Brzev, S., & Dasgupta, K. (2020). Probabilistic seismic risk assessment of India. *Earthquake Spectra*, 36(1_suppl), 345–371. <https://doi.org/10.1177/8755293020957374>

- Martins L, Silva V (2021): Development of a Fragility and Vulnerability Model for Global Seismic Risk Analyses, *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering* 19 6719–6745...
- Pagani M, Monelli D, Weatherill G, Danciu L, Crowley H, Silva V, Henshaw P, Butler L, Nastasi M, Panzeri L, Simionato M, Vigano D (2014): OpenQuake Engine: An open hazard (and risk) software for the Global Earthquake Model, *Seismological Research Letters*, 85 (3), 692-702
- Riga E, Karatzetzou A, Mara A, Pitilakis K (2017). Studying the uncertainties in the seismic risk assessment at urban scale applying the Capacity Spectrum Method: the case of Thessaloniki. *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*, 92, 9–24
- Riga E, Karatzetzou A, Apostolaki S, Anastasiadis A, Lontzetidis K, Pitilakis K. (2020): How much may the precision of site conditions modelling affect seismic risk assessment at large urban scale? The case of Thessaloniki, Greece. *New Zealand Geotechnical Society 2020 Symposium*, 15-17 October, Dunedin, New Zealand.
- Riga E., Apostolaki S., Karatzetzou A., Danciu L, Pitilakis K. (2022): The role of site modelling in seismic hazard and risk assessment at urban scale. The case of Thessaloniki, Greece. *Italian Journal of Geosciences* (accepted for publication)
- Silva V, Crowley H, Pagani M, Monelli D, Pinho R. (2014): Development of the OpenQuake engine, the Global Earthquake Model's open-source software for seismic risk assessment. *Natural Hazards*, 72 (3):1409-1427.
- Silva, V., Crowley, H., Varum, H., & Pinho, R. (2014a). Seismic risk assessment for mainland Portugal. *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering*, 13(2), 429–457. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10518-014-9630-0>
- Washington, D.C.: World Bank. *The Gross domestic product 2020 (GDP)* 1 July 2021.
- Woessner J, Danciu L, Giardini D, Crowley H, Cotton F, Grünthal G, Valensise G, Arvidsson R, Basili R, Demircioglu MB, Hiemer S, Meletti C, Musson RMW, Rovida AN, Sesetyan K, Stucchi M, The SHARE Consortium (2015): The 2013 European Seismic Hazard Model: Key Components and Results, *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering*, 13 (12), 3553–3596.